

Research Article

A Study on Nutrients Accumulation in Agricultural Runoff by Using Organic Manure in Form of Pellets: Case Study of Muyange Marshland in RWANDA

Ronaldo Muvunyi^{2*}, Rémy Patrick Tumwizere¹, Félicien Majoro¹, Concilie Mukamwambali³, Anabella K. Umuhoza¹, Danny Kanamugire¹ and Emmanuel Hagenimana¹

¹Department of Civil, Environmental and Geomatics Engineering, College of Science and Technology, University of Rwanda, P.O. Box 3900, Kigali, Rwanda

²Civil Engineering and Environmental Technology, Taiyuan University of Technology, No.79 West Street Yingze, Taiyuan 030024, Shanxi, P.R. China

³Department of Mathematics, Science and Physical Education, College of Education, University of Rwanda, P.O. Box 5039, Kigali, Rwanda

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 17 April, 2020; Online: 18 April, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3756242>

Abstract: This paper conducts a comparative experimental analysis to investigate the nutrients accumulation in agricultural Runoff by Using Organic Manure in Form of Pellets. the aim consists of protecting water resources against over enrichment of nutrients from steep agricultural lands, and providing with environmental management practice for sustainable and climate resilient soil fertility management in Rwanda. Different type of household waste was collected and mixed with cow dung, then dried and crushed to make a better experimental sample. The manure laboratory test was conducted to measure the amount of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium to determine its fertilizing value compared to standards of leguminous crops and NPK. A part of manure flour was wetted to form Pellets (size 2cm x 1cm x 0.5cm) which had been used for the fertilizer deep placement (FDP) application in two first sets of land, and the remaining manure was mixed with surface soil “(for fertilizer surface application (FSA)) on another same size of land. Soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-15 cm from the surface. the samples were air dried and ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve. Beans were planted on two sets of land one with FDP and the other with FSA, the same to eggplant on the same size of land. The analysis result of the mixed manure shown that Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium were found to be 0.943%, 0.0197% and 3.93% respectively for which phosphorus was not falling in the standard range of (1.6-4.2) % while others fall in their ranges (0.5-1.9) % and (2.3-12) % respectively [17]. On the other hand, the analyzed runoff from the FSA and FDP fields shown that the concentrations of nutrients (mg/l) were different: in the FSA runoff, nitrate, phosphate and potash were 0.12, 0.32 and 11.8 whereas in the FDP runoff the concentrations were only 0.044, 0.13 and 4.3 respectively. The advantageous result is that manure fertilizer was found to be effective for leguminous crops due to its way of keeping the soil fertility and increasing the water holding capacity. The study concluded that FDP should not be applied to legumes without considering the size of pellets. Large size pellets do not

improve the crop yield, moreover, not suitable for the crops. Hence FSA is more acceptable for the vegetables.

Key words: Pellets; Manure fertilizer; Fertilizer Deep Placement (FDP), Fertilizer Surface Application (FSA); Agriculture runoff.

Introduction

The intensification of agricultural use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides has caused increased environmental degradation [15]. Organic agriculture has become a widely-used alternative to conventional farming practices [15]. The major factor contributing to reduced agricultural productivity is soil fertility depletion in steep lands [1] caused by continuous cropping without addition of adequate fertilizer, irregular release of nutrients and wash away of mineral fertilizer due to non-application of fertilizer in deep placement [3]. Nutrients runoff from agriculture causes algal blooms and eutrophication, which pollutes aquatic ecosystems [16].

The problem of nitrogen and phosphorus over-enrichment in water bodies (rivers and lakes) is predicted to endure if drastic measures are not put in action. This may lead in deterioration of air and water quality not forgetting soil productivity reduction due to fertility depletion from fertilizer wash away [4]. This results in deceleration of crop growth mechanism leading to famine in developing countries that main have an agriculture based economy[5].

This paper addresses nutrient over-enrichment control in large ecosystems and a good management of nutrients cycle in a more cost-effective, sustainable and resource efficient way. Nutrients over-enrichment of water bodies is a direct consequence of these elevated nutrients levels and is an increasing problem worldwide.

Data and Methods

Site description

Kigali city is located near the geographic center of Rwanda (Figure 1). The field study was held in MUYANGE marshland located in the City of Kigali, KICUKIRO District, KAGARAMA Sector.

Figure 1: Districts of Kigali City

This research was not limited to one place on the side of organic wastes as raw materials due to the need of most effective organic material suitable to a certain type of plant. The work was concentrated in the laboratory, fields of application and in waste collection works as well as the likely purpose is to valorize organic waste to effective and competing manure fertilizer.

Experimental Design and Treatments

Manure is a valuable farm resource that provides nutrients for crop production. Before spreading manure on the fields, it is better to know what it contains to supply the right concentration in nutrients to the soil and not creating any environmental trouble [7].

A manure test measures the amount of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and several micronutrients to determine its fertilizing value. Nutrients in the manure can match to the requirements of a specific crop. Additional nutrient sources can be applied to balance what is lacking in the manure [8].

That's why the collected waste has to be crushed and different type of wastes have been mixed to get a better experimental sample.

The experiments have been carried out during 4 consecutive months from February 2016 to May 2016. These experiments started by selecting the site where to apply the manufactured manure and deciding suitable crops to that land. A plot of (15m over 7m) was selected in the City of Kigali, Kicukiro District, Kagarama Sector, MUYANGE cell. This project included a direct partnership with a farmer who had a plan to introduce leguminous crops in his land so that we proposed him to apply this research project on fertilizers on his field. According to the objectives of this research, the land is steep and drains to the marshland into a small stream of water and the place is liked to

leguminous plantation as well as the farm was prepared for this type of crop. Beans and eggplants were chosen, planted and fertilized differently: beans were planted on two sets of land one for FDP another for FSA, the same to eggplants on the same size of land. Manure flour were wetted to form Pellets (size 2cm x 1cm x 0.5cm) (Figure 2) which had been used for the fertilizer deep placement application in two first sets of land and the two remaining sets the surface soil was mixed with manure in the form of flour.

Figure 2: Form of pellets during fabrication

Figure 3: Drying pellets on a sheeting

Sampling

The sample collected to be analyzed in the laboratory as field soil sample, manure sample and field runoff sample with adequate details like extraction depth and the number of days the sample is to be stored (either disturbed or undisturbed). Also, samples are numbered for identification.

Soil and Organic Material

Soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-15 cm from the surface. After removing weeds, plant roots, stubbles, and stones, the samples were air dried and ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve. The samples were then stored in clean plastic bags until further chemical and mechanical analyses. Some samples have been extracted for moisture content test and pH while others for manure composition test are collected and stored for further laboratory analysis.

Organic wastes

Data collection and processing of this research focused on composting house hold wastes (unconsumed food, grasses from gardens and other organic unused materials) from different homes, which took a long time at around 5 months to be degraded due to difference in component decomposition rate. After that sample collection the wastes were mixed with low amount of cow dung.

Manufactured manure (from COPED Ltd organic fertilizer manufacturing company)

Using household wastes which are collected all around in Kigali domestic homes as raw materials, this company is in charge of collecting and recycling solid wastes. For this company, organic materials are put in process of decomposition and dried after in order to produce a conservable organic manure, whereas the component in COPED collected house hold wastes are similar to the above collected organic materials (unconsumed food, grasses from gardens, pills and other organic unused materials).

Laboratory Analysis [18]

Materials: Photo spectrometer, analytical balance, filter paper, beakers, funnel, burette, Erlenmeyer, graduated cylinder, pestle, oven, pH meter, thermometer, watch glass, electric furnace, hot plate, flame photometer, distiller, heater, porcelain dish, glass rod, vacuum desiccator and 500-ml digestion flask.

Reagents: Sulfuric acid concentrated, distilled water, hydrochloric acid, potassium sulphate, sodium hydroxide solution, iron sulphate, copper (II) sulphate, boric acid, methyl red, bromocresol green, selenium.

Physical Parameters

Soil moisture content:

Two important forms of water present in soils are: (i) absorbed/adsorbed water; and (ii) free water. They are interchangeable depending on the degree of moisture saturation and temperature. Therefore, moisture estimation is not such critical to determining the quality of soil. The method used is either:

- gravimetric method;
- vacuum desiccator method;
- Oven drying method

Preferred method (Oven drying method)

The sample must be measured before being dried in order to know the total mass ($M_t = M_s + M_w$) where by M_w is mass of water and M_s is a mass of soil. There follows the drying of the measured sample as bellow.

The procedure is:

1. Weigh (accurately) 100 to 150g of sample in a porcelain dish, and keep it in oven drier for 24 hours.
2. Take the weight again after 24 hours. The loss in weight is equal to moisture content in the sample.

Observations

The relevant calculation is:

$$\% \text{moisture} = \frac{M_w}{M_d} * 100$$

Where: M_w = weight in grams of lost water after drying in 24hrs it is a difference between the original mass of the sample before drying and the new sample mass after drying ; M_d = total weight in grams of the soil sample after drying.

According to the procedures: the soil sample is originally taken and measured on the beam that resulted a mass of 129g and after 24hrs the mass was 118.04g showing that mass of evaporated water was 10.96g.

Relevantly if the mass of water is as such and the total mass of an extract was 129g: the soil moisture content is 0.093 for the bare soil or the soil that is fertilizer free.

Moisture content for the fertilized soil

Preferred method (Vacuum desiccator method)

With the vacuum desiccator method, the free moisture present in the fertilizer is absorbed by the desiccator (sulphuric acid), and the loss in weight is reported as moisture. This method is suitable for fertilizers such as calcium ammonium nitrate, Diammonium Phosphate (DAP), and NPK complexes.

In this method, the sample is kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. Free moisture present in fertilizers is absorbed by the acid, and the loss in weight of the sample is recorded as the moisture content in the sample.

The procedure is:

1. Weigh (accurately) 5 g of sample in a porcelain dish, and keep it in a desiccator for 24 hours.
2. Take the weight again after 24 hours. The loss in weight is equal to moisture content in the sample.

The relevant calculation is:

$$\% \text{ moisture} = \frac{B-C}{C-A} \times 100$$

Where:

A = weight in grams of the porcelain dish;

B = weight in grams of the porcelain dish plus the fertilizer sample;

C = weight in grams of the porcelain dish plus the fertilizer sample after desiccation for 24 hours.

Soil pH test

- The material got separated on the ¼ in. (6.3 mm) sieve. Only the passing ¼ in. (6.3 mm) material is to be used for testing.
- 30±0.1 g of soil weighted and placed into the glass beaker.
- 60 ml of distilled water was added to the soil sample. Stirred to obtain soil slurry and then covered with watch glass.
- The extracted sample stood for one hour, stirring every 10 to 15 minutes. That was to allow the pH of the soil slurry to stabilize.
- After one hour, the temperature of the sample was stabilized by measuring the temperature of the extracted sample and adjusting the temperature controller of the pH meter to that of the sample temperature. This adjustment was done just prior to testing.
- The pH was standardized by means of standard solution provided. Temperature and adjustment were performed.
- Immediately before immersing the electrode into the sample, the sample had to be well stirred with a glass rod.
- Place the electrode into the soil slurry solution and gently turn beaker to make good contact between the solution and the electrode.
- To allow the pH meter to stabilize, a range of 30seconds to one minute with electrode immersion into the soil slurry solution is required, as well as it had an auto read system with which it automatically gets signal when stabilized.
- Read and record the pH value to the nearest tenth of a whole number. If the pH meter reads to the hundredth place, a round off rule will apply as follows: If the hundredth place digit is less than 5, leave the tenth place digit as is. If it is greater than 5, round the tenth place digit up one unit. If the hundredth place digit equals 5, round the tenth place digit to the nearest even number.

- The electrode was well rinsed with distilled water and dabbed lightly with tissues to remove any film formed on the electrode.

Caution: Do not wipe the electrodes as this may result in polarization of the electrode(s) and consequent slow response.

NOTE 1 - To standardize the pH meter, use the 7.0 pH buffer standard solution plus the other standard solution which is nearest the estimated pH value of the sample to be tested. If the manufacturer's instructions indicate a method other than that noted above, then those instructions must be followed.

NOTE 2 - When immersing electrode(s) into the glass beaker, care should be taken not to hit the bottom or side, causing damage to electrode(s).

NOTE 3 - If polarization does occur, as indicated by a slow response, rinse the electrode(s) and dab lightly again.

Observations:

The soil without fertilizer is said to have pH of 5.98 acidified and after fertilization the soil pH increases to an alkalized value of 6.48

Fertilizer nutrient composition tests (NPK)

Total nitrogen [10] (TN) (Kjeldahl method)

Digestion of total nitrogen

- 1 g of an analytical sample weighed and put in a 500-ml digestion flask;
- 5 g of potassium sulphate (K_2SO_4), copper sulphate, iron sulphate and selenium were weighed as catalysts, and further add 20 ml of sulfuric acid concentrated;
- The solutions were shaken to mix and heated gently until bubbles cease to form,
- After bubbles cease to form the solution was heated until white smoke of sulfuric acid evolves and ignited until organic matters were completely digested.
- Standing to cool, a small amount of water was added and mixed well by shaking and transferred to 250-mL volumetric flask with water, and further mixed by shaking,
- After standing to cool, distilled water was added up to the marked line to make the digestion solution.

Distillation of total nitrogen

- 20ml of digestion solution was taken and introduced into a distillation tube
- 20ml of distilled water was added
- 20ml of sodium hydroxide solution (50%) was added
- The solution was extracted and the distillate was collected in Erlenmeyer of 500ml containing 10ml of boric acid
- 50ml of distillate were collected approximately.

Titration

The obtained solution was titrated with H_2SO_4 - 0.1N until pink color appears and the quantity in ml of H_2SO_4 - 0.1N used was noted.

Figure 1: Distillation process arrangement

1.1.1 Total phosphorus (TP) (Kjeldahl method) “Total-Phosphate determinations”

Digestion

- 5 g of catalyst, and 20 mL of sulfuric acid concentrated were added and shake to mix and heat gently.
- 5g of an analytical sample weighed to the order of 1 mg, and put it in a 300mL digestion flask,

- After bubbles cease to form, the solution was heated until white smoke of sulfuric acid evolves and ignited until organic matters were completely digested (After the change in the color of the solution ends, the solution was heated for not less than 2 hours).
- Standing to cool flask with water, and further mix by shaking.
- After standing to cool, distilled water was added up to the marked line
- Filtration was done with 3 types of filter paper to make the sample solution.

Figure 2: Filtration to make the sample solution

Total potassium (TK)

In all potassic fertilizers, K is generally present in water-soluble form. Therefore, it is estimated directly in fertilizer solution either gravimetrically, volumetrically or flame photo-metrically. In manures and organic fertilizers, wet digestion with acid is required prior to determination of K in order to bring the element into solution by digestion.

The methods used for K determination in fertilizers and manures are:

- Gravimetric perchloric acid method;
- Gravimetric chloroplatinate method;
- Gravimetric and volumetric cobaltinitrite method- Flame photometer test.

Flame photometer test

The procedure is:

- K extraction: Preparation of sample solution

- Dissolve a known weight (2.5 g) of straight K fertilizer (MOP, SOP, potassium magnesium sulphate) in 200 ml of distilled water, and make the volume up to 250 ml for estimation. For NPK complex fertilizers or NPK fertilizer mixtures, dissolve the sample in 125 ml of water, add 50 ml of 4% ammonium oxalate solution, and boil for 30 minutes; after cooling, filter through dry No. 12 filter paper, and make the volume up to 250 ml for further estimation.
- Transfer 15 ml of aliquot of sample solution to a 100 ml volumetric flask and add 2 ml of 20% NaOH and 5 ml of HCHO.
- Add 1 ml of standard Potassium Tetraphenyl Boron (STPB) solution for each 1% of K₂O expected in the sample plus an additional 8 ml in excess in order to ensure complete precipitation.
- Dilute to volume (100 ml) with water, mix thoroughly, let it stand for 5–10 minutes, and pass it through filter paper (or equivalent).
- Transfer the mixed filtered solution in flame photometer with different standards and distilled water to measure the K absorbance.

Results And Discussions

Manure application

The fertilizer deep placement FDP is highly different from the fertilizer surface application FSA in the following circumstances

Table 1: Effect of manure application on water quality and crop yield

Manure application method	Water quality	Crop yield
FSA	Lower	Higher
FDP	Low	High

Though FDP provided an acceptable crop yield is not as efficient as FSA due to the application of large size which lead to unexpected crop yield that was reduced compared to that found in FSA. Regardless of the size constraint in the application of FDP, the quality of water was found to be of absolute low content of nutrient in contrast of FSA method.

Figure 3: Eggplant plantation with both FSA and FDP (Site of application)

Figure 4: Beans plantation showing both FSA and FDP Site of application)

The FSA and FDP differ in terms of crop yield and vegetation appearance Figure 3 and Figure 4. The germination of beans is more significant by FSA than in FDP field part. The pictures include the shading waters which are below the FDP and FSA fields respectively. The nutrients were found to be highly concentrated in the shading water below the FSA field compared to that below the FDP field part.

Moisture Content Results

The moisture content of the fertilized and unfertilized soil differ respectively as 6% and 8.04% this shows the reduction in the soil water content and soil is needing much water.

Since the fertilized soil is in need of water, the irrigation is applied to the soil needing water and the water holding capacity is not the same as before fertilization. If the soil is finer, the water holding capacity is higher than before fertilization.

pH

Fertilization of soil increases the pH value from 5.94 to 6.45. This means that the acidity of the soil has been neutralized by the application of organic manure resulting to a basic condition of the soil as an indicator of the increased soil fertility.

Nutrient Accumulation Effects

The used organic manure contributed to the soil water holding capacity since it was tested to be completely nutrient rich. Having N, P and K presence, placing it in the deep soil is to hide the nutrients that are available to crop growth away from runoff path and prevent from other environmental impact. Organic manure increased soil fertility more than chemical fertilizer.

Environmental Effects

One of the worst-known environmental responses to high levels of nutrients is eutrophication i.e the enrichment of water bodies, which can promote the growth of algae. When nutrients (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus) and sunlight stimulates algal growth (e.g., algae, seaweed, and phytoplankton), this increases the amount of organic matter in an aquatic ecosystem over time.

Due to high water holding capacity in FDP, nutrients are not easily washed away. But in FSA, when there is excess runoff, nutrients are washed away thus surface water can contaminate water supplies and then potentially harms human and animal health. Considering air pollution due to fertilizer surface Application, organic manure might release unpleasant odour and it might blow in the atmosphere. Exposing the manure or providing a direct space with the atmosphere by fertilizer surface application due to reaction that can happen when nutrients get wetted by rain or irrigation water and heated by the sun which favours them to disperse into the air or when blown by the wind. All those circle like actions change the air composition whereas with Fertilizer Deep Application, nutrient are buried in deep soil that air pollution would not be an issue.

Human Health Effects

In addition to Harmful Algal Bloom (HABs), excess nutrients in water have other known health effects, depending on the type and condition of exposure. Conjectural evidence suggests that an excess of both nitrogen and phosphorus may contribute to infectious and non-infectious pathogens, potentially causing epidemic conditions. This however, is a difficult relationship to make given the interrelated nature of humans and wildlife disease emergence.

Parameters Tested and Benefits

Total Nitrogen

Table 2: Nitrogen Content in Fertilizer

Sample	Volume (ml)	Concentration (ppm)
S1	46	0.35
S2	38	0.27
S3	50	0.39

Compared to the standard of interpretation, the present total nitrogen content with an average of 0.943% is found to be in the range because the same as household and ash manure should be (0.5 – 1.9)% [17]. This fact has substantiated how much the fertilizer contains desirable amount of nitrogen to the extent it can be considered for plants need of nitrogen rather than other nutrient.

Total Phosphorous

During experiments, the results show the presence of total phosphate contained in the fertilizer, the below table shows different concentrations and percentage calculation of phosphate (PO_4^{-3}) from different samples as well as trials.

Table 3: Phosphate P_2O_5 table showing concentration and percentage

Sample	Concentration (ppm)
S ₁	1.18
S ₂	0.95
S ₃	0.82

Unfortunately, the average (0.0197%) of results in performed trials does not fall in the range (1.6 – 4.2) % [17]. This fact has shown how much the fertilizer contain less materials rich in phosphorus to the extent it cannot be considered.

Total Potassium

Table 4: Concentration and absorbance of potassium standards

Concentration(ppm)	absorbance
1	0.01
5	0.048
100	0.514

The absorbance (Capacity of a substance to absorb light of a specified wavelength) has been measured by a Flame Photometer. The concentration of total phosphorus obtained are shown in the Table 5.

Table 5: Potassium K calibration table showing concentration absorbance and percentage.

K Concentration in (ppm)	K absorbance
99.24	0.51
96.04	0.494
99.44	0.511

Fortunately, the average (3.93%) of results in performed trials does fall in the range (2.3 – 12) % [17]. This fact has substantiated how much the fertilizer contain desirable amount of potassium to the extent it can be considered for plants in need of potassium rather than other nutrient.

Nutrient concentrations in runoff

MUYANGE site runoff eroded nutrients towards a surface water way as it is shown in the Table 6, dissolved potash, nitrate and phosphate in runoff from MUYANGE watershed during rainfall season.

Table 6: Dissolved potash, nitrate and phosphate in runoff from MUYANGE watershed

Nutrients eroded	Concentrations in mg/l due to FSA	Concentrations in mg/l due to FDP
Nitrates	0.12	0.044
phosphates	0.32	0.13
potash	11.8	4.3

Concentrations in runoff are primarily functions of the vegetation types in the source areas. Table shows average dissolved potash, nitrate, and phosphate concentrations in runoff from the most abundant plant types of the watershed, measured on the field plots over four months of natural precipitation. Since average nutrient concentrations often differ significantly according to the method of fertilizer application that was used, the concentrations were separated into methods Fertilizer Deep Placement (FDP) and Fertilizer Surface Application (FSA) in order to know which is against water pollution or protect the quality of water.

Nitrogen

As stated previously, nitrogen is a mobile nutrient that can occur in a variety of forms. Nitrogen is affected by chemical and biological processes that can change its form and transfer it to or from water, soil, biological organisms, and the atmosphere. The increasing use of reactive nitrogen in agriculture also increases the potential for nitrogen to be lost to the environment as ammonia (NH_3), ammonium (NH_4), nitrate (NO_3), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and nitrous oxide (N_2O). Excess nitrogen can be transferred to water sources in a number of ways, including:

- ✓ Soil erosion either by wind or water, erosion can move soil particles containing nitrogen into surrounding waterways.
- ✓ Runoff dissolved nitrogen, either as inorganic (e.g., nitrate) or organic (e.g. Manure) fertilizer, applied directly to the soil surface can wash away the field with moving water (e.g., rain, snowmelt, or irrigation) if not incorporated into the soil.
- ✓ Leaching water moving through the soil profile can transport dissolved nitrogen to underground water sources or through tile drains surface water.

Phosphorus

Phosphorus is an immobile nutrient and therefore is generally transferred to water through sediment-based runoff or erosion. To a higher extent, phosphorus transported from cultivated lands is associated with soil particle and organic material erosion during flow events (e.g., rain or irrigation). To a lesser extent, phosphorus leaching can occur through subsurface flow, primarily transported in drainage waters (e.g., through tile drains). While some soils can absorb applied phosphorus, they are not infinite sinks. Once the capacity of the soils to absorb phosphorus is exceeded, the excess will dissolve and move more freely with water. Continued application of phosphorus beyond plant requirements can be a major cause of soil phosphorus saturation; both surface runoff and subsurface flow are linked to soil phosphorus concentration.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

This research has revealed the benefits of using FDP method in Rwanda but it is convenient to follow rules and regulations to reach the anticipated crop yield. This technique has shown the best results and improvement after application. The degree of soil water holding capacity increased due

to the use of appropriate amount of organic manure with the best and relevant method of application.

The FDP method of application should only be used with the help of skilled labours bringing the guidelines in order to reach the high crop yield and maintained water quality due to the decreased surface nutrient erosion by the compacted and deep-placed manure pellets.

4.2 Recommendations

All application methods either FDP or FSA should depend on the type of crop by differentiating the crop roots and how adapting it is on that method of application. By considering these 2 methods, the leguminous crops are surface application friendly.

There should be a consideration of agricultural land properties such as pH and land soil moisture before applying certain crop on the land. In MUYANGE marshland there are some areas with mixed crops and where all crops are not suitable for the watershed's moisture and pH.

It is recommended to prioritize the use of organic manure for the leguminous crops since it is the best way to help them continuing grow quickly and moreover organic manure improves soil texture as it increases soil water holding capacity. The use of organic manure instead of chemical fertilizer also makes the legumes grow in their normal period which is different from using chemical fertilizer that makes them grow unexpectedly and later will affect human health by cancer problems. [10]

Fertilizer deep placement is suggested to be applied for the agriculture that is done in water ways like MUYANGE marshland as it has been shown that FDP prevent nutrient accumulation in agricultural runoff by hiding nutrients in deeper soils and availing them to plants. It should also be applied on small agricultural land since it carries much financial and man power effort. [11]

Fertilizer surface application is suggested to be applied in the mountainous cropping since it provides the higher yield compared to its adversary method and it is giving high holding capacity and then preventing leaching effect to the ground water which is present under different mountainous regions.

References

[1] Waterquality, "WATER QUALITY," san francisco bay, san francisco, 2003.

[2] MINAGRI, "Strategic plan for the transformation of agriculture in Rwanda," Kigali, 2013.

- [3] Hauggaard-Nielsen, H. "Nitrogen dynamics following grain legumes and subsequent catch crops and the effects on succeeding cereal crops," *Nutrient cycling in agroecosystem*, vol. 84, pp. 281-291, 2009.
- [4] Sharpley, T. "Agricultural Phosphorus and Eutrophication second edition," United States Department of Agriculture, WASHINGTON DC, 2003.
- [5] Wiebe, K. and Gollehon, N. (2006). Agricultural resources and environmental indicators. United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), *Economic Information Bulletin No. (EIB-16) 239 pp.*
- [6] Bala, A. "Organic matter utilization and the determinant of organic manure use by farmers in the Guinea savana zone of Nigeria," *Innovation as the key to the green revolution in Africa*, vol. 2, pp. 965 - 974, 2011.
- [7] Lekasi, J. K. (2002). Manure Management Methods to Enhance Nutrient Quantity and Quality on Smallholdings in the Central Kenya Highlands. *International Journal for Sustainable Production Systems*, Volume 19, Issue 4.
- [8] Manitoba, "manure management facts", 2009.
- [9] Manitoba, "effects of manure and fertilizer on soil fertility", 2013.
- [10] Wang, Z. "Review effects of fertilization and other agronomic measures on nutritional quality of crops," *Journal of the science of food and agriculture*, vol. 88, pp. 7-23, 2008.
- [11] Sh. Islam¹, F. "Effects of NPK Briquette on Rice (*Oryza sativa*) in Tidal Flooded Ecosystem," *Effects of NPK Briquette on Rice (Oryza sativa) in Tidal Flooded Ecosystem*, no. ISSN-1729-5211, p. 7, 2011.
- [12] Y. Demirel, Energy, Production, Conversion storage, Conservation and Coupling., London, : British library london, 2012,.
- [13] National Organic Standards Program. 2013. Title 7 Part 205, National Organic Program. United States Department of Agriculture. Retrieved from <https://www.ecfr.gov/cgi-bin/retrievedECFR?gp=&SID=15784F4dfd0f285214693435613ceecf&n=7y3.1.1.9.32&r=PART&ty=HTML>.
- [14] Pimentel, D., Hepperly P., Hanson, J, Douds, D., and R. Seidel. 2005. Environmental, Energetic, and Economic Comparisons of Organic and Conventional Farming Systems. *Bioscience* 55: 573-582.

[15] Pimentel, D., Hepperly, P., Hanson, J., and Seidel, R. (2005). Organic and Conventional Systems: Environmental and Economic Issues. Report-05. Cornell University, Ithaca, USA.

[16] Beman, J., Arrigo, K. and Matson, P. 2005. Agricultural runoff fuels large phytoplankton blooms in vulnerable areas of the ocean. Nature 434: 211-214.

[17] A. K Dhama. 1996. Organic Farming for sustainable Agriculture. Agro Beneficial Publishers. Rampul, Nepal.

[18] R. B. Bradstreet, "kjeldahl Method for Organic Nitrogen," vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 185-187, 1954.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info